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Impact of Gandhiji's visit in Rayalaseemaduring Non-Co operationMovement :A Study

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Introduction

Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi, (2 October 1869-30 January 1948), born at Porubandar in Gujarat, emerged as a new Messiah in Indian politics in 1919 and dominated Indian freedom movement down to 1947. Nehru wrote, "Gandhi's influence is not limited to those who agree with him or accept him as a national leader, it extends to those also who disagree with and criticize him... To the vast majority of India's people, he is the symbol of India determined to be free, of militant nationalism, of a refusal to submit to arrogant might, of never agreeing to anything involving national dishonour. Though many people in India may disagree with him on hundred matters, though they may criticize him or even part company from him on some particular issue, at a time of action and struggle when India's freedom is at stake they flock to him and look up to him as their inevitable leader".¹

The early nationalist leaders like M.G Ranade, Dadabhai Naoroji, R.C Dutt, Tilak, Lala Lajpat Rai and Bipin Chandra Pal spoke at length about the poverty of the masses and Britain's exploitative role in India but hardly did anything for amelioration of the lot of the poor masses. Gandhi made it clear that the Congress represented the dumb, semi-starved millions scattered over the length and breadth of India and he initiated practical steps to improve their social and economic lot. His emphasis on eradication of untouchability, uplift of the Harijans, revival of Khadi industry and adoption of hand-spun and hand-woven cloth as the national uniform were all calculated to improve the lot of the poor masses living in the villages.²

As a fighter for India's freedom, M. K. Gandhi was a saint-politician who employed moral means for the attainment of political ends. He used "soul-force" against brute force. Gandhian methods and techniques of non-violent methods yielded rich dividends. Not only was the hatred for slavery and love for freedom firmly planted in the Indian mind but the imperial rulers also came to realize that British rule in India was wrong and unjust. The ruling classes in Britain realized that Gandhi and congress could arouse the masses against the Government at any time and make its functioning difficult. On the basis of conversation with Winston Churchill, George-VI noted in his diary on 28 July 1942, "He (Churchill) amazed me by saying that his colleagues and both or all three parties in Parliament were quite prepared to give up India to

the Indians after the war. He felt they had already been talked in to giving up India. Cripps, the press and the U.S public opinion have all contributed to make their minds up that our presence in India is wrong and has always been wrong for India".³

About Rayalaseema

Rayalaseema of the British times in India includes the districts of Bellary, Cuddapah (Kadapa), Kurnool, Anantapur and Chittoor. The region is located between 12° 37'-16° 18' northern latitude and 75° 40'-79° 30' eastern longitude. It had a territorial extent of 83,600 sq km. Under the Subsidiary Alliance system, concluded between the Nizam of Hyderabad and the English East India Company on 24 October 1800, the Nizam ceded to the Company⁴ the area corresponding to the modern districts of Bellary, Kadapa and Anantapur and parts of Kurnool and Chittoor districts as the "Ceded Districts" and constituted it as an administrative unit of the Madras Presidency in 1800 with Thomas Munro as Principal Collector. The State of Hyderabad was incorporated into to the Republic of India with Operation Polo in 1948. On the basis of a Gentlemen's Agreement of 1 November 1956, the State Re-organization Act Andhra Pradesh brought into existing by merging the Telugu-speaking areas of the already existing Hyderabad State with Andhra State. Now under the Andhra Pradesh Re-organization Act of 2nd June 2014, Rayalaseema incorporated in Andhrapradesh State.

In the late 16th century, "Rayalavariseema" and "Rayalaseema" were used to refer to a part of the present Rayalaseema⁵ were used to refer to a part of the present Rayalaseema⁶. For reasons not clear, this name went out of use, and the term "Ceded Districts" given by the British rulers in AD 1800 continued to be in vogue for the region till 1928. As the nationalist spirit was growing in the country, this term came to be disliked by the enlightened Andhra leaders. At one of the Andhra Conferences held at Nandyal in 1928, Pappuri Ramacharyulu proposed, at the instance of Chilukuri Narayana Rao, the revival of the earlier name "Rayalaseema" for the region for the memory of the famous Rayas of Vijayanagara, who ruled it as a part of their empire for well over three centuries, from the mid-fourteenth century to the mid-seventeenth century. The proposal was unanimously carried and the name popularised and got entered in the official records.⁷

From the time the freedom movement came under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi in 1920, nationalist consciousness began to be reinforced in all the sections of people. With Mahatma Gandhi tours and his speeches in public meetings in Rayalaseema, common people of the region were also convinced of the need to work for the cause of the country and were thoroughly inspired to work for the ongoing nationalist movement.

Mahatma Gandhi's tour during Non-cooperation

The Non-Cooperation inaugurated lead by Mahatma Gandhi on 1st August, 1920, was a unique event in Indian history. Never before the country witnessed such awakening, activity, unity and determined effort on the part of the people. The movement was formally inaugurated to get until the Khilafat and Punjab wrongs righted and Swaraj established by peaceful means⁸. The resolutions were reaffirmed at the AICC Nagpur session (1920) under the presidentship of the Vijayaraghavachariar from Madras.⁹ Immediately after the Nagpur session, Mahatma Gandhi made an extensive tour of the country in order to popularise the Non-cooperation movement. The Mahatma rightly guessed that the emotional people of Andhra would support his call for Satyagraha strongly unlike the calculating Tamils. So he made Konda Venkatappayya member of the Congress Working Committee and sometime its General Secretary¹⁰.

It was when Andhra was agog with the Non-Cooperation Movement that the Congress decided to hold the AICC session at Vijayawada. The Working Committee that met in Vijayawada on from 31st March and 1 April 1921 was of a very momentous nature where important decisions were taken. It is an unique event in Andhra history. Andhra hosted the conclave of the national leaders for the first time. Konda Venkatappayya, Gollapudi Sitarama Sastri met Mahatma Gandhi and Kasturba at Puri and invited them to Vijayawada. Hearing about the coming of Mahatma Gandhi along with Kasturba, and other prominent national leaders like Vallabhbai Patel, Jawaharlal Nehru, Motilal Nehru, Lala Lajpat Rai, Deshbandhu Chitranjan Das etc, people from all over Andhra went in thousands to Vijayawada. In spite of poor communication facilities, people trekked the long distances on foot or in bullock carts to attend the session, which looked more of a '*mela*' or religious festival than of a political gathering to discuss the serious issues confronting the nation. To get over their fatigue, visitors used to sing national ballads on their way.¹¹ The AICC session was held at Vijayawada, what is now called Gandhinagar, where there were no houses but some thorny bushes.¹² The vast gathering of nearly two lakhs people who came mainly to have a glimpse of the 'Mahatma' became unmanageable

and stampede was feared. But the splendid work done by 'Ramadandu', the volunteers' corps of Andhra Ratna Duggirala Gopalakrishnayya, saved the situation.¹³ Addepalli Ramaseshaiah Chetty was the president of the reception committee.¹⁴ Kalluri Subbarao of Hindupur in Anantapur district participated not only at Vijayawada AICC session but also acted as a volunteer. The other prominent leaders from Rayalaseema like Ananthasayanam Iyengar, Neelam Chinnappa Reddy, Tarimella Subbareddy, N. Sankar Reddy and others attended the AICC at Vijayawada. This session had great impact on the progress of the freedom struggle in Rayalaseema.¹⁵ The Madras government guessed the impact of Gandhiji's visit thus:

"The expected visit of Gandhi and the congress leaders to Vijayawada can hardly fail to give impetus to the movement in that part of the Presidency."¹⁶ People returned to their places with the message of non-violence, non-cooperation and spread it among those who had not the fortune to attend the Vijayawada session.¹⁷

Gandhiji's tour of Rayalaseema

Soon after the conclusion of the AICC session at Vijayawada, Gandhi accompanied by Deshabhakta Konda Venkatappayya undertook a tour of Andhra. His tour promoted the khaddar programme and intensified the struggle against the foreign rule. He visited some of the coastal districts and addressed meetings at Kakinada, Rajahmundry, Eluru, Machilipatnam, Guntur, Vetapalem, Bapatla, Chirala, Nellore and other places.¹⁸ He informed the gathering about the significance of Khaddar, Hindu Muslim unity, anti-untouchability, temperance campaign and promotion of Hindi language.¹⁹

In September-October 1921, Mahatma Gandhi undertook again a tour of Rayalaseema, accompanied by Konda Venkatappayya, Shoukat Ali and others. Several towns in Rayalaseema, Tirupati, Cuddapah, Tadipatri, Kurnool and Bellary were included in his tour. This major programme was arranged by Gadicharla Harisarovvottama Rao, then the Secretary of Andhra Provincial Congress Committee.²⁰ Gandhiji's tour of Rayalaseema began with his arrival at Chittoor at 5AM on 28th September 1921. The warmth of seven thousand people welcomed him and his associates. The function hosted by the town's municipality lasted for 10 minutes, for both the people and their leader realized the importance of the time available.²¹ Gandhi then proceeded to Tirupati, a temple town in Chittoor district, where he had similar attention of the local leader and the people, both Hindus and Muslims. The volunteers looking offer the calm at the meeting attended by sixteen to twenty thousand people, were handled by Venkata Rao and Mohammed Osman Sahib and other prominent

citizens of the town²². Gandhi then proceeded to Rajampeta, where he delivered a speech on Swadeshi, spinning and removal of untouchability, and the local Vysyas felicitated Mahatma Gandhi. Then he left for Cuddapah. The 28th of September was a red letter day in the annals of Cuddapah town on account of the Gandhiji's visit. Gandhiji, accompanied by Maulana Subhani Azad, arrived at 4.40 pm and they were given a warm welcome by the people of Cuddapah. Both the leaders were taken in procession to the meeting place. A huge gathering of masses attended the meeting and most of the people wore popular white Khaddar clothes and Gandhi caps. Gadicharla Harisarvottama Rao translated Gandhiji's speech into Telugu.²³

Then Mahatma Gandhi left for Tadipatri (Anantapur district) on 29 September 1921. Gadicharla Harisarvottama Rao and Konda Venkatappayya accompanied him on the tour. At 5:30 in the morning Tadipatri, a small town, witnessed a spectacle of fifty thousand people from the same town and surrounding villages. This indicates the zeal of the masses. In the same forenoon of the day, the leader covered two engagements, one, a meeting on the riverbed of the Pinakini, passing by the town, and another, a meeting arranged by the ladies of the town. An address on behalf of the ladies was read and presented to the leader by Smt. Kamamma, wife of the local Congress Secretary, K. Srinivasacharlu. Forty thousand people of all classes were fed at Tadipatri town on this day, which suggests the magnitude with which the arrival of a national leader was treated and to what extent the people were aroused to the nationalist cause. The artists from Nosam of Kurnool district utilised the occasion and exhibited their art pieces, which included paintings on Khaddar cloth. The leader took interest in the exhibition and appreciated the skills of the Kurnool artists, particularly those coming from the panchama segment. In the afternoon of the same day, Gandhiji and his associates proceeded to Kurnool.

While Gandhiji was on his way to Kurnool, people in large numbers gathered at the railway stations at Gooty and Dronachalam. In spite of midnight of 29-30 September, people at Dronachalam station demanded to have a *dharsan* (beholding) of Gandhiji. But Konda Venkatappayya addressed the gathering that Mahatma Gandhi was fast asleep and it would not be good on their part to disturb him. However, he told the people, as the wish of Gandhiji that by wearing Khaddar clothes all should adopt Swadeshi, the source of getting independence for the country, give up all expensive fairs and festivals and work with calm.

Mahatma Gandhi reached Kurnool town on Friday the 30 September 1921. Medam

Venkayya Sresti took the leader to his house and presented a purse of Rs 1,116 with all reverence and respect. People arrived from different places to town to welcome him enthusiastically. Along with Gandhi, Moulana Abdul Khader Azad Subhani, Konda Venkatappayya and other prominent leaders also visited Kurnool. Gandhiji wanted that there should be no procession or demonstration. Hence the people decorated the main streets with festoons, welcome arches with "May gods protect Mahatma Gandhi" etc, on the banks of the sacred Tungabhadra river. The Khilafat and Congress volunteers managed the crowd to a perfect peace without the help of the police.²⁴ Mahatma Gandhi addressed the gathering of 25,000 people. After the prayers of Hindus and Muslims, Gadicharla Harisarvottama Rao presented Khaddar cloths to Gandhiji. Later the chairman of Kurnool Municipal Council presented an address printed on Swadeshi paper. Mahatma Gandhi reiterated the use of Khaddar, Hindu-Muslim unity, and giving up of drinking, gambling as well as prostitution. Gandhiji and Subhani stressed in their speeches the need of the Hindu-Muslim unity. Besides, Gandhi dwelt at length on the issue of untouchability and the need to work for its eradication. A Swadeshi box containing an address of the people, with silver toy moving Charka attractively mounted on, was gifted to Mahatma Gandhi. Gandhiji appreciated and auctioned charka for 450 Rupees, which was donated to Khilafat and Tilak Swaraj Fund.²⁵

Conclusion

Mahatma's visits promoted khaddar, women and Harijan uplift, and intensified the struggle against the British Government. The speeches by the Mahatma at the meetings he had both in urban and rural areas had an electrifying effect on the people both literate and illiterate. They began participating in the movement with a new found vigour necessary to implement what the leader advocated on various issues relevant to the then prevailing political and social issues. Thus Gandhian methods convinced the rulers that transfer of power into Indian hands was inevitable and it could no longer be delayed.

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